

INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING ENGLISH. PRACTICAL BASIS OF RESEARCH OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *It is necessary to organize and implement the process of teaching English in educational institutions. Knowing how to organize it correctly will help us to solve the goal and task. Implementation of this depends on the teacher's knowledge, skills, abilities, conditions, availability of tools, and his familiarity with them. This article examines the issue of introducing innovative technologies in English language teaching.*

Keywords: *innovation, education, educational efficiency, pedagogy, English language, educational system.*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, teaching using innovative methods of teaching foreign languages, especially English, is gaining importance in the preschool education system and in general education schools. Based on the initiatives and innovations of pedagogues-teachers, content development is observed in all educational systems. It also has a positive effect on the development of the education system as a whole.

In a word, innovation means a new approach to solving a problem in a specific field of activity.

As in all countries, the place and role of the state, society, local and social organizations, higher and lower management bodies, mutual unity and cooperation between them is important in the modernization of the educational system in Uzbekistan. At the same time, the flow of information enters the social life of the Republic at a rapid speed and covers a wide range. Receiving information at a rapid pace, analyzing, processing, theoretically summarizing and delivering it to students are one of the urgent problems facing the educational system. The application of pedagogical technology to the educational process serves to positively solve the above-mentioned current problem.

Within the framework of the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the national personnel training program, a comprehensive system of teaching foreign languages is being created in our country, that is, a system aimed at forming a harmoniously matured, educated, modern-thinking young generation and further integration of the Republic into the world community. At the same time, the analysis of the current system of organizing foreign language learning shows that educational standards, curricula and textbooks do not fully meet the requirements of the time, in particular, the demand for the use of advanced information and media technologies. Education is conducted mainly in traditional ways. The organization of continuous learning of foreign languages at all levels of the educational system, as

well as the improvement of teachers' qualifications and the provision of modern educational and methodological materials require further improvement.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment (in the family, in the community) or in an organized class. Knowledge of language phenomena is studied theoretically. In our era of growing international relations, knowledge of languages and multilingualism are of great importance.

Today, as a result of the emergence of a new scientific direction in the field of pedagogy - pedagogical innovation and the idea of renewing the educational process, a new direction in the pedagogical activity of a pedagogue-educator, the concept of innovative activity of a pedagogue, appeared. This requires pedagogues-teachers to regularly develop their skills and research. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev took this into account and said, "That's why we rely on you first of all to bring up young people in the spirit of national and universal values, modern knowledge and professions, mastering foreign languages, people who are loyal to our Motherland and people"[1], they express great confidence in pedagogues-teachers.

In contrast to the careful development of the methodical development of the lesson that motivates the teacher to perform effectively, educational technology is oriented towards the activity of students, and it serves to create the necessary conditions for the independent mastering of educational materials, taking into account the individual and joint activities of students.

As an element of the structure of the pedagogical innovation process, the news carrier is characterized in terms of the unity of perception, assimilation and evaluation of innovation, goal setting and goal achievement. The totality of motivation (I want), theoretical (I can do), technological (I do) and result (I can get) aspiration and readiness forms the innovation educational system of pedagogues of educational institutions. Indeed, advanced pedagogical technologies increase the productivity of the educational process, form the independent thinking process of students, increase students' enthusiasm and interest in knowledge, develop the skills and competencies of solid assimilation of knowledge, free use of it in practice.

In general, pedagogy is rapidly developing, concepts such as innovation in education, innovative activity, innovative pedagogy, management of innovative processes in education, learning foreign languages, teaching in a foreign language have appeared. The teaching of foreign languages, especially English, in educational institutions is connected with the creation of innovative educational theory. This is the reason for forming an attitude to the child in the process of education, absorbing the achievements of foreign education, in order to achieve certain successes in the educational process, to improve the educational efficiency, to ensure the socialization of the individual, to reform the educational system by introducing pedagogical technologies into the educational system.

The goal of learning, generalizing and disseminating best practices in foreign language teaching is also aimed at achieving positive results. Advanced work experience consists of research in general (foreign language teaching experience) or some sub-areas (for example, creating a language environment at the beginning of the lesson, practical teaching of a difficult grammatical phenomenon) using the analysis/synthesis method. Those who choose to teach a foreign language as a profession have the task of becoming fully aware of the theory of teaching this language. The science of teaching is illuminated by the science of methodology, the word *methodike* is Greek and means "a set of methods for doing something according to the purpose".

Innovative study of the educational system today is determined by the application of new methods and methods of teaching, which have been tested in practice, to the educational process. The purpose of the educational process must be planned in advance. One of the goals is to ensure that the educational environment is comfortable and boring, the student needs to realize that he has the opportunity to fully master the subject of the lesson, that he has enough intellectual potential, so that the product of the educational process becomes an activity.

In the interactive teaching method, all students actively participate in the lesson, as well as students understand that they can rely on the information they know, think, and use, and develop skills for the lesson. Each student personally participates and contributes to the result of working together and being of the same opinion. Students exchange experience with their knowledge, skills and qualifications, ideas, views, opinions, methods of activity.

Classes based on pedagogical technology provide an opportunity for students to express their attitudes to important life achievements and problems, to think, and to justify their points of view.

In order to solve the problems faced by the educational system, the innovative processes taking place today require independent and free-thinking individuals who are able to absorb new information and evaluate the acquired knowledge by themselves. Therefore, the role and importance of modern teaching methods - interactive methods, innovative technologies in the educational process of educational institutions is incomparable. The role of the teacher in interactive lessons is partly to direct the activities of students to achieve the goals of the lesson.

Modernity and traditionalism made it possible to analyze the process of formation and development of the innovative pedagogical activity of the pedagogue-educator. Person-centered learning, first of all, changes the paradigm of education. If earlier teaching was considered a priority in the education system, now in the age of information society, the priority is directed to teaching to read. For this reason, it is necessary to replace the teacher-textbook-pupil paradigm of education with the textbook-teacher paradigm. The teacher will have a new status, now his task will be to teach students to organize independent learning activities, to acquire knowledge independently and to apply it in practice. For such purposes, the teacher should choose teaching methods and technologies in such a way that he should create an opportunity for students not only to acquire ready-made knowledge, but also to search for knowledge from various sources, acquire it independently, form a personal point of view, justify it, and use previously acquired knowledge to obtain new ones. Such training can also be called developmental.

The English teacher should know the correctness of the methods, ways, and exercises he uses, what kind of knowledge he is imparting to the pupils, students, and identify their shortcomings, and the results of the examination will be accurate. English language learners and students are interested in knowing the results of their knowledge. If these parties are interested in English language teaching in educational institutions and make the right conclusions based on the results of the examination, English language teaching will be in the direction of general education, educational, practical, developmental, as desired, in accordance with the requirements of the program, and the goals will be realized.

A person attains spiritual maturity, as a rule, through hearing and seeing (observation) and, moreover, through reading. Among three activities in information gathering, listening comprehension is the most important. It is interesting that the question is not asked, can you speak? Perception is a measure of intelligence. Speaking and listening comprehension means speaking.

While acquisition of knowledge is considered an important factor in the development of thinking, any acquisition of knowledge does not have a developmental effect on a student's thinking. For this, it is necessary to activate knowledge and forms of activity. A simple return of acquired knowledge will not be enough to develop independent thinking of pupils and students. Active cognition, independent thinking activity is very necessary.

Innovative activity implies a creative approach of an educational institution and a pedagogue to mastering existing forms and tools for improving their profession. It should also be recognized that scientific concepts and classifications that are stable and acceptable to everyone about innovations in education and innovative pedagogical activity have not yet been fully formed. "Of course, science is looking for ways to solve the contradiction between technology and personality in the educational process. The concept of the educational process, along with the concepts of teaching and educational technologies, is part of methodological knowledge, or in its scientific analysis and practical organization, knowledge of educational systems, legality, systematic and technological approaches in pedagogy is combined"[2].

CONCLUSION

Thus, in modern education, innovation, more specifically, the use of pedagogical and educational innovations, is gaining importance. Therefore, globalization and the informatization of society require the use of effective methods and tools in the educational process in non-traditional forms, as well as an innovative approach to the formation of educational materials and their practical use. Pedagogical innovations change the internal structure of the pedagogical system.

In conclusion, nowadays, teaching foreign languages, especially English, using innovative methods of teaching in the educational system and educational institutions is gaining importance. In a word, innovation means a new approach to solving a problem in a specific field of activity.

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